

Personalized Ayurvedic Management of Post-Viral Gastrointestinal Discomfort: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT: Ayurveda, the science of life, emphasizes a holistic approach to treatment, considering food, regimen, and medicine as key aspects of healing. This case report presents the Ayurvedic management of a 52-year-old female patient experiencing severe lethargy, abdominal pain, and burning sensation following a viral fever. The treatment was customized based on her Prakriti and Dosha status, demonstrating the effectiveness of personalized Ayurvedic interventions.

KEY WORDS: Jwaram, Chikitsa, holistic treatment

INTRODUCTION

Ayurvedic Chikitsa (treatment) is based on restoring the equilibrium of Doshas, which varies among individuals. This personalized approach distinguishes Ayurveda from other medical systems. Diseases are not treated with a one-size-fits-all approach but rather tailored to the patient's constitution, food habits, and lifestyle. This report presents a case that highlights the Ayurvedic methodology of treating post-viral gastrointestinal disturbances using food as medicine alongside herbal interventions.

CASE PRESENTATION

Patient Information

- **Age:** 52 years
- **Sex:** Female
- **Chief Complaints:** Severe lethargy, abdominal pain, burning sensation in the abdomen
- **Date of OPD Visit:** 28/05/2024

History of Present Illness

- The patient developed symptoms of **chickenpox** on 03/05/2024.
- On 09/05/2024, fever worsened, associated with nausea; treated at an allopathic hospital with **antacids and antiemetics**.
- Discharged on 13/05/2024 with symptomatic relief but persistent **hard, dry, and irregular bowel movements**.
- Gradual onset of abdominal pain and burning sensation; further allopathic treatment included antiemetics.
- An **ultrasound scan (25/05/2024)** revealed **Grade 1 fatty liver** with no other significant changes.

Clinical Examination

- **Prasna Pareeksha:** Revealed digestive discomfort post-viral illness.
- **Sparsha Pareeksha:**
 - Mild warmth over the upper abdomen.
 - **Grade 5 tenderness** over the abdomen.
 - **Nadi** showed **Jwaritham** characteristics despite a normal thermometer-measured temperature.
- **Darshana Pareeksha:** Puffiness and **dainyam** (paleness) of the face.

Diagnosis

- **Ayurvedic Understanding: Kaphaja Jwara with Pittanubandhatvam.**
- The original **Pitta Jwara** (chickenpox) was treated symptomatically with **antiemetics**, leading to increased **Kapha dominance**, worsening digestive issues.

Treatment Protocol

1. Internal Medications

- **NisundiShadangamChoornam**, prepared as **Panajalam**, was administered frequently for its **Pittahara, Pachana, and Jwarahara** properties [1].
- **Vilwadi Gulika**, ground with **ArdraKaswarasa** and honey, was given in small doses to reduce fever-related complications [2].
- **AmruthadiKashayam (Pachanamritham Kashaya Choornam)** administered in **half of the normal dose** twice daily before meals [3].

2. Dietary Management (Anna - Peyadi Krama)

- **Peya** prepared with **NisundiShadangamChoornam** was given for the first four meals [4].
- From the fifth meal, **Vilepi** was introduced with **NisundiShadangamChoornam**.
- Gradual transition to **Mudga Yusha**, followed by **Odana**, and then **Prakriti Bhojana** as the patient regained appetite [5].

3. External Therapies

- **Dhanyamladhara** was applied locally over the abdomen to reduce tenderness and warmth [6].
- **VaiswanaraVasthy** was administered on 30/05/2024 to promote **Anulomana** and **Rookshana** [7].
- As the patient gained strength, **SarvangaDhanyamladhara** was performed for systemic benefits.

Outcome

By the **fifth day of treatment**, the patient was relieved of all symptoms, demonstrating the effectiveness of the holistic Ayurvedic approach.

DISCUSSION

- The treatment plan focused on **Pachanam therapy**, counteracting the aggravated **Kapha** and supporting digestion.
- The administration of medicine was tailored based on the patient's **Agni** (digestive strength) to ensure proper assimilation.
- The dietary regimen followed **Samsarjana Krama**, a structured reintroduction of food post-illness, crucial for **Jwara recovery** [8].
- **External therapies** complemented the internal medications, enhancing therapeutic efficacy.

CONCLUSION

This case illustrates the significance of **personalized Ayurvedic treatment** in post-viral digestive disturbances. By assessing the patient's **Dosha status, Agni**, and disease stage, a combination of internal medications, dietary modifications, and external therapies effectively restored health. This emphasizes the need for an **individualized approach** in clinical Ayurveda.

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